

Governance for Data Collection, Sharing, and Use in Smart Cities: Institutional Challenges in Facilitating Innovation while Addressing Societal Concerns in Shenzhen

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Abstract

Data governance is a critical section in the construction of smart cities. Current research still has gaps in the overall data governance mechanism, particularly how data openness promotes innovation in detail and potential data security and privacy risks. Taking Shenzhen, China, as a case, this paper aims to explore collecting, sharing, using, innovation, security, and privacy of data governance, focusing on analyzing how data openness promotes social innovation and how the government will deal with potential risks of data security and privacy. At the end of the article, there are some policy implications. As for institutional innovation, the Shenzhen Municipal Government is the leader in the smart city construction, issuing many documents and supporting policies to guide the data collection, sharing, and application. Meanwhile, the government encourages enterprises to co-design the smart city through general contracting, subcontracting, and government purchases. Besides, in terms of data security and privacy protection, when framing the governance system, policymakers should consider the policy feasibility, implementation scope, and the consistency of relevant policies to reduce the confusion of enterprises and the public.

Keywords – smart city; data governance; open data; data management; data security and privacy

1 Introduction

Currently, about 55% of the world's population lives in urban areas, and this proportion is expected to increase to

68% by 2050 (UN, 2018). The rapid development of urbanization has brought about many challenges, such as population management, traffic congestion, environmental protection, and safety governance. The dilemma facing modern urban governance requires cutting-edge technologies, citizen engagement, and effective mechanisms to provide an effective solution to tackle social challenges. The smart city as an ideal development vision for urban governance began to arouse intensive discussions in the world.

However, the smart city's conceptualization is ambiguous, and there is no unified definition in the literature (Tranos & Gertner, 2012; Meijer, 2015). Most researchers agree that the application of intelligent technologies is the key characteristic of the smart city (Tan & Taihagh, 2020). These studies emphasized that, in the smart city system, data is recorded, transmitted, and stored through the perspective layer and network layer, which are based on the Internet of Things (IoT) and other advanced technologies. Moreover, through the real-time analysis cloud-computing based platform layer, the collected data provides the decision-making basis for city managers to improve the efficiency of urban governance (Effendi, Syukri, Subiyanto, & Utdityasan, 2016; Tan & Taihagh, 2020). Some researchers interpret the smart city from the perspective of human resources. Their studies emphasized that citizens as the core of smart cities can create public value through engaging in public governance and public policymaking in the era of the smart city (Tan & Taihagh, 2020). Other scholars stress the concept of collaboration in the context of a smart city. These studies highlight that the governance of smart city relies on the collaborative mechanisms of several actors (Broccardo, Culasso, & Mauro, 2019). Under the paradigm of new public governance (NPG), the principle of improving

policymaking and public services through collaborative governance and participatory governance has been more and more recognized. The collaborative governance network composed of multiple stakeholders (e.g., government, enterprises, academia, non-profit organizations, and the public) plays an increasingly important role in the development of smart cities (Broccardo, Culasso, & Mauro, 2019). Most of the existing literature focuses on the application of technology-driven smart cities. Fewer researches study smart cities from the perspective of smart governance. Questions such as defining ownership, usage right, data management among multiple stakeholders during the co-construction and co-governance of smart city, how the organizational setting and regulation formulations facilitate the institutional innovation of information sharing while privacy protection in the context of the smart city remains unanswered. Solving these questions will help governments break the information silos, enhance the cross-sectoral collaboration in the government departments, and encourage social participation in public governance.

Nowadays, most countries in the world are actively involved in the construction of smart cities, among which Europe, North America, Japan, and South Korea are in a leading position. As the pioneers of the smart city 1.0, in 2004, the South Korean government launched the "UKorea" strategy, using the Internet Technologies (IT) such as wireless sensors to help Korea to become a smart society; in 2006, the Singapore government formulated the "Smart Nation" initiative and regarded it as a leading initiative in the economic and social area; in 2010, the European Union (EU) proposed intelligent Growth as one of the critical tasks in the "Europe 2020 Strategy" (Deloitte, 2019). While in the era of Smart City 2.0, the gap of urbanization between developing countries and developed countries has gradually narrowed. Asian countries, with the highest growth rate in urbanization, begun to invest heavily in smart city projects. Notably, China has become the leading country in the construction of smart cities in the world. With more than 490 smart city pilot cities, China's smart cities account for 48% of the smart cities worldwide (Deloitte, 2019). According to Deloitte's latest report, "Super Smart City 2.0", Shenzhen ranks first among all China's smart cities in the dimensions of strategy, penetration and innovation, and second in the technology basis (Deloitte, 2019). As one of the earliest cities in China to explore the construction of a smart city, Shenzhen has a complete electronic industry chain. It has established the smart city industry cluster. The critical characteristics of Shenzhen's smart city construction are "Citizens-oriented" and firmly cooperating with Shenzhen local high-tech enterprises. In the field of Big data, Internet of Things (IoT), Cloud Computing, and Artificial Intelligence (AI), there are many representative high-tech enterprises that are cooperating with Shenzhen government

departments to co-construct the various government data platforms, such as Shenzhen municipal government data opening platform, Shenzhen big data resource management center, and Guangdong province data opening platform.

Current research still has gaps in how data governance is established and managed in facilitating innovation while addressing societal concerns in smart cities in China. Inspired by the great achievement of the smart city in Shenzhen, this research will focus on the research questions of how each data governance activity process, why open data can promote innovation, and how the government should do to face the challenges of data security and privacy. In more detail, this article will explore the Shenzhen's successful experience in public-private partnership (PPP) in the construction of government data platform, to prove the innovative institution of data ownership, sharing, and using, and discuss the solution between sharing and privacy of data.

2 Literature Review

This section aims to summarize the current research status of data governance in smart cities, mainly involving the concept of data governance, collecting, managing and using data in an open data environment, and institutional challenges in potential data security and privacy risk. At present, these domains have a profound research foundation. This part begins with the definition of data governance, moving to explain the details of data mechanisms and data security concerns and privacy concerns.

2.1 Smart city and data governance

In the era of information, communication, and technology (ICT), big data is one of the foundations of smart city development. The focus of smart city governance is data governance, including data infrastructure construction, urban data management, and platform software design. (Barns, 2018) However, data governance is a comprehensive concept, and current research in this area has focused on defining it.

The Data Management Association (DAMA) (2016) defines data governance as the exercise of authority, control, and sharing decisions over data asset Management. Therefore, data governance can be seen as high-level planning and control of data management. Besides, some researchers describe data governance as a framework or system for decision making and accountability. Panian (2010) believes that data governance is a system of decision-making rights and responsibilities for

information-related processes. Data managers execute according to established models that describe who can take action with what information, and when and in what circumstances, and what methods should be used. Niemi (2011) argues that data governance is a specific framework of decision rights and responsibilities used to encourage desirable behaviors in data use. To promote ideal data applications, data governance develops and implements data policies, guidelines, and standards consistent with its mission, strategy, values, norms, and culture. Similarly, Otto (2011) said that data governance is a framework for assigning rights and responsibilities related to decision-making within a company so that data can be fully processed as corporate assets.

In summary, data governance is the guiding principle for managing and using data. With a clear understanding of this concept, this article will focus on the comprehensive data collection, sharing, and application mechanisms underlying the content of smart cities.

2.2 Data collection, sharing, and use

When implementing smart city policies, the government usually plays the role of the decision-maker and organizer. They take the lead in data governance and coordinate with stakeholders to build smart cities. At present, most research in this field starts from the perspective of government, describes the significance of open government data, elaborates on the construction of urban data-sharing platforms by different stakeholders, and analyzes the promotion effect of open data on urban innovation.

2.2.1 Open government data

The government can engage the public in building smart cities through open data programs. Bertot et al. (2010) believe that open data is a promising concept that can promote the cooperative production of new public services. It will improve citizen participation in social innovation and transparency of public sector information and improve government decision-making. Cegarra-navarro et al. (2012) consider that the Internet can make local governments more transparent and provide a wide range of information and services. However, group software can connect government agencies and the public more closely and create opportunities for collaboration. Clarke & Margetts (2014) Argue that big data can be used as a tool to support mutual understanding between citizens and governments, thus greatly influencing public decision-making and improving public services. In general, open Data and open Government programs promise to show the public how the government works. In turn, the government uses big data to understand citizens' behavior and analyze the advantages and disadvantages of policies.

Other studies have focused on the transparency of government data. Data transparency can generally be regarded as a public value and code of conduct, which can fight corruption and make information easy to obtain and use (Ball, 2009). However, more and more people require government agencies to release data, which indicates that citizens' rights to data cities are synchronized with their distrust of the government (Bertot et al., 2010). Some studies believe that open data does not meet its advocates' expectations. Open data does not increase transparency, and that open data sets cannot better clarify or improve government processes (Clarke & Margetts, 2014). Therefore, the Open Data Initiative must be part of the government's efforts to improve transparency, enhance civil rights, and promote innovation and reform in public services (Ojo et al., 2015). The combination of accountability and transparency can better promote the launch of open data movement by national governments, universities, and research teams (Pereira et al., 2017).

2.2.2 Data collection

When it comes to collecting the open data, the existing research mainly focuses on analyzing how the government organizes the various stakeholders, not involving the specific data collection mechanism of various stakeholders in society to build a data platform. Conradie & Choenni (2012) consider that the public sector should play the role of a data provider, the researchers to classify data and education, and serve as a creative industry data to the user. In the study of Jetzek et al. (2014), electronic information systems in the context of data can effectively reduce each benefit phase's cost. They will support the construction of data platforms and the use of data to add value.

In addition to government agencies, the private sector, such as companies, may also become big data providers. In general, a typical smart city project involves not only local governments and large multinational companies, but also the participation of local SMEs, to translate general technical solutions into local needs (Caragliu & Del, 2019). The government's task is to understand citizens' needs, preferences, behaviors, and administrative interactions through data collected through social media operations and other channels and to improve policy formulation and services (Clarke & Margetts, 2014).

Zuiderwijk & Janssen (2014) pointed out that in addition to considering cooperation with other groups to improve the degree of data openness, the use of data should also be incorporated into the organization's daily workflow. Mulder (2015) believes that releasing public data by uniting different sectors of society in the way of co-creation can establish a sustainable mechanism of open data and stimulate social innovation at a deeper level.

However, the government's open data initiative is not just about making information available. It is about building more applications to enrich people's lives. It is about people making and designing cities together.

2.2.3 Data sharing

Data sharing in smart cities is mainly done through government statistics websites, specialized data platforms, and mobile phone applications. There is little research in this area, and it focuses on the advantages and disadvantages of sharing data in various ways to make recommendations. Cegarra-navarro et al. (2012) pointed out that the key for local governments to share data lies in how they deal with the Internet, social media software, and collective systems. The Finnish government has used a policy tool called Living Labs to organize a competition for open data applications to collaborate to build an innovative platform around open data that aims to provide smart services (Hielkema & Hongisto, 2013). Lourenco (2015) evaluated the open government portals of different countries and finally concluded that these sample government portals often lack some critical structural and organizational elements necessary to support the participation of ordinary citizens in the accountability work. A portal, for example, seems to function as a simple data repository. Although all portals provide some form of metadata for each dataset, it is less useful and often challenging to understand. Different data sets have different metadata structures. However, most data sites do not have a complete listing of possible metadata fields and their descriptions.

2.2.4 Data using and innovation

There are few existing studies on data use and innovation, the main content of which is to criticize the inconvenience of data use and prove the effect of open data on innovation, and the lack of research on how to use data and how to promote social innovation.

Conradie & Choenni (2012) believe that there are several obstacles in opening data in practice. From the user's point of view, accessing the right database and making full use of it are the significant challenges they face. The main challenges for data providers are the lack of technology to store data, the lack of knowledge about what data can be released, and the economic cost of making it public. Clarke & Margetts (2014) pointed out that perhaps the most significant criticism of the Open Data Initiative can be made in terms of the quality and accessibility of data. Open data sets are released in raw form so that developers and analysts can manipulate the data without formatting restrictions. This also makes the data quite difficult for ordinary citizens to access.

Roy (2014) believes that open data can promote broader collective innovation and a more overall catalytic capacity of governance renewal. Jung & Park (2015) showed that open data policies promoted the proliferation of innovative products and the development of entrepreneurial industries, so they should be incorporated into the creative economy ecosystem as long-term policies. Caragliu & Del (2019) demonstrated that smart city plans could promote scientific and technological innovation in cities through empirical research. The number of patents filed by cities with smart city policies is higher than the EU average, especially for high-tech patents. Bonina & Eaton (2020) believes that in order to use open data for innovation, an ecosystem consisting of demand-side and supply-side participants of open government data platforms must be cultivated. In this ecosystem, third-party innovators need data sets from government agencies to create services.

2.3 Challenges in data security and privacy

As for data security and privacy protection, the research mainly stays at a superficial level to explain why there are potential risks and point out related challenges. Few articles offer policy recommendations on maintaining data security and privacy, and most are studies in the field of information technology.

Kulk & Loenen (2012) indicated that information sharing might increase the chance of disclosing private and sensitive data, such as personal name, email and postal address, date of birth, geographical location, bank account number, photo, and political/personal views. Trust in institutions diminishes when their data sharing creates privacy risks that can harm citizens and individuals. Elmaghraby & Losavio (2014) believe that innovation has accelerated the construction of smart cities around the world, creating new economic opportunities and posing challenges to our data and privacy security. Rosnay et al. (2014) argued that a joint technical and legal framework could be used to manage data of a different nature and address legal, cultural, and institutional issues in a cross-sectoral manner.

All stakeholders, including researchers, governments, businesses, and other organizations, understand that advanced information technology-based smart city platforms need to adopt advanced privacy protection measures and security mechanisms. According to the present challenges to Privacy and Data Security from the Smart City Data system mainly consist of Privacy avoidance policy, medium-term Privacy policy, medium-term, and Data Provenance (Dhungana et al., 2015). People's concern over Data Privacy stems from who will deal with their Data and their degree of trust from the different Data management agencies. He believes that

personal information can be classified according to personal or non-personal, as well as service or regulatory purposes (Van Zoonen, 2016).

3 Collection, Management, Application, Institution, and Privacy

Since current research still has gaps in the overall data governance mechanism, particularly how data openness promotes innovation in detail and potential data security and privacy risks in China, this paper's research unit takes Shenzhen city as a case. It illustrates the data collection, use, and sharing mechanism of Shenzhen in the smart city context. The study also introduces institutional innovations and privacy protection regulations to explore the development pathway and the solutions to privacy concerns in the age of the smart city. This paper adopts qualitative research to obtain primary data through in-depth interviews with the local high-tech enterprise that participates in the smart city platform. The question covered the collection, use, and sharing methods of Shenzhen smart city. Besides, we will also use the existing secondary data such as public government documents collected from the online government information platform and the research report on the smart city from consultation companies. These data will be used to analyze the role positioning and shared cooperation of various stakeholders under the data management mechanism.

3.1 Data collection

The Shenzhen government agencies is mainly responsible for collecting urban data. However, data is an asset, and the data collected by each public sector is different. For example, for individuals, the public security agencies, civil affairs departments, and medical authorities will have their domain related database. Besides, for enterprises, government departments will collect their business registration information, tax information, and social security information, etc. In general, all information related to city life is collected by different public sectors.

The public sector collects data mainly through self-reporting and community workers collecting door-to-door. The government authorities maintain a high degree of confidentiality over data relating to personal privacy, which is voluntarily provided by the public on informed consent. Furthermore, all the agencies and individuals have to undergo a very complex and strict approval procedures if they want to access the data. They can only get big data that does not involve personal information. Small groups fewer than 20 people are almost impossible to get. Also, those technology enterprises only help build information platforms and do not directly participate in data collection.

3.2 Data sharing and using

Data sharing in Shenzhen is the government's responsibility, mainly presenting in public data platforms, such as designated website and mobile application. The stakeholders of data sharing include other public sectors, the public, and enterprises. This section will introduce the construction, operation, and data sharing and using.

At present, the smart city data platform in Shenzhen is mainly outsourced by the government to technology enterprises. The specific forms include enterprise general contracting mode, subcontracting mode, government purchase mode. For general contracting mode, enterprises directly sign agreements with the government for the whole project, which is generally the cooperation mode for large projects. The enterprise is responsible for the project and needs to undertake most of the platform development work. However, some tasks in the project may also be subcontracted to other partners when existing technology deficiency. The advantage of this model is that the general contractor is fully responsible for the project. In case of any problem with the products delivered by the subcontractor, the government can directly hold the general contractor responsible for the project without coordinating multiple stakeholders. Secondly, subcontracting mode means that the government signs agreements with different enterprises in different sectors to complete a project. The advantage of this model is that the government can take advantage of enterprises in various fields. Still, the disadvantage is that the government needs to balance the relationship between multiple stakeholders. Thirdly, the government can purchase enterprises' products on an annual basis rather than setting up separate projects. This model is generally applicable to small open data projects, and large projects cannot take the form of government purchases.

After built the smart city platform, all the data will be delivered to operate by the government. In the early stage of platform handover, the cooperative enterprise will be responsible for technical maintenance. Once the data operation becomes stable, it will be transferred to the government, and then it will be independently operated. However, it does not rule out that the government will set up a subsidiary to run the platform. This way can ensure data confidentiality, but there is an advantage that maybe the government does not have enough maintenance technicians.

The sharing of data is responsible for government departments, but different sectors are account for different data. Some of the data are available to all the public will be displayed on government-designated websites or other software. However, some private data can only be passed

between the public sector, and the evaluation process is rigorous. Now the main obstacle for data sharing is coordination between different departments. The fundamental problem lies in human interaction rather than institutional issues. Besides, data cleansing and governance is also a problem. Much of the data cannot be presented in its natural form and needs to be standardized to make it easy for users to manipulate. The city's government information center usually account for this, and the sheer volume of data slows down the open data progress.

The data users are mainly government departments who use data to maintain social order and serve the public. For financial data, for example, the public sector is mainly used for regulatory functions. Police will use the data to crack down on financial crimes. Of course, there will be personal use of the data. For example, researchers will use publicly available city-data.

3.3 Institutional Innovations of Smart City in Shenzhen

Shenzhen's informatization development has experienced long-term exploration and practice. It has always been at the forefront in institutional innovation and top-level planning in China, laying a foundation for the subsequent construction of a "people-oriented" smart city. Shenzhen informatization development has gone through four stages: information infrastructure construction (1997-2001), e-government construction (2002-2010), smart city construction (2011-2015), and new-type smart city construction (2016-present) (CETC, 2017).

3.3.1 Information Infrastructure Construction

In 1997, Shenzhen began to develop its information infrastructure and hosted the first national informatization working meeting. The meeting defined China's national informatization system for the first time and included the Internet as part of the national informatization system (CAC, 2009). The meeting was the beginning of informatization in Shenzhen. In terms of infrastructure construction, Shenzhen began to establish a unified communication network platform, develop various types of databases, and promote the network interconnection in all districts.

3.3.2 E-government Construction

In 2002, Shenzhen began to shift its focus of the information construction to e-government. Shenzhen was one of the first pilot cities for e-government services in China. The priority of Shenzhen's e-government is to

combine the reform of the government review and approval system with information technology to promote the sharing of information resources and promote "people-oriented" public services. The specific measures for e-government reform include promoting and improving various online service systems for enterprises and the public (e.g., electronic security authentication exchange platform). The e-government projects in Shenzhen involves many filed of people's livelihood, such as electronic tax filing services, online business application services, and community information services (Xinhua Net, 2002). In order to improve an e-government policy and regulation system and establish an institutional e-government mechanism, in 2006, the Shenzhen Municipal Government launched a series of e-government policy documents called "Shenzhen E-government. " Pilot '1+8' Documents" (Beijing International Institute of Urban Development, 2006).

Table 1 Shenzhen E-governance Pilot "1+8" Documents

Guideline Policy Documents	Supporting Policy Documents
Opinions on strengthening e-government work	The Provisions of Shenzhen Municipality on the Disclosure of Government Information
	The Interim Measures for the Administration of the Construction of E-Government Projects
	The Interim Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Administration of Government Information Resources Sharing
	The Interim Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Administration of Public Website
	The Interim Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Standardization Administration of E-Government
	The Interim Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Administration of Information Digitization of Community Government Affairs
	11 th Five-Year Plan for Shenzhen E-government Affairs
	Interim Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Construction and Administration of the Internal Computer Network of the Party and Government Organizations

Source: Organized by authors

3.3.3 Smart city construction

Shenzhen's investment in and emphasis on information technology build a solid foundation for constructing a smart city (LIN, 2017). However, in promoting the development of a data-driven city, Shenzhen still faces the dilemmas of "governance fragmentation, information chimneys, and information silos. " Different data systems of different government departments use different data formats, different data standards, and different data

jurisdictions, leading to low administrative efficiency, and making it extremely difficult to implement collaborations within the government departments. Thus, in 2011, Shenzhen began to promote smart city construction to reshape the city's information system. Furthermore, according to the "Guidelines of Smart Shenzhen (2011-2020)", Shenzhen proposed to optimize the smart city operation mode, establishing an operation mechanism that is led by the government, co-constructed by the service operators, system integrators, and jointly participated by multiple actors such as solution providers, equipment suppliers and value-added service providers (Shenzhen Industrial and Information Technology Bureau, 2013). Ultimately, Shenzhen aims to drive smart cities towards the road of sustainable development.

Table 2 Representative Market Participants and the Role of Participants in Smart City

Services operators	System integrators	Hardware application developers	Software application developers	Third-party service providers
Telecom operators such as China Telecom, China Mobile, China Unicom	China Electronics Technology Group Corporation	ICT equipment suppliers such as Huawei	Tsinghua Tongfang	Tencent, Ping An Technology and Vanke
The operators provide government and industry customers with solutions and integrated operations of network connections, cloud platforms, and big data applications	The general contractor of the construction and operation of smart cities. Provide a complete packaged software, hardware, and solutions to customers	Based on hardware equipment, the suppliers comprehensively use emerging technologies such as AI and IoT to provide solutions and "cloud + digital" ecology	Provide professional software products and design smart city's applications	Mainly composed of Internet, financial, and real estate companies; Provide Internet portals, operating systems, or city service applications for smart cities. Some Chinese real estate companies are transforming towards service providers and operators of the smart city community

Source: Organized by authors, referred to China's Smart City Industry Research Report (2019), CAICT.

In 2013, Shenzhen began to implement the "Netting Project". That means government uniformly manage the information resources of 15000 grids in Shenzhen through establishing a public primary information resources database, forming a team of information collectors, creating a comprehensive information collection system, and launching a social management network (LI, HAN, & CUI, 2014).

Figure 1 Operation Mechanism of Smart City in China

Source: Redrawn by authors, referred to the smart city report of EO Intelligence, China.

Figure 2 The System of "Netting Project" in Shenzhen
Source: Organized by authors

Table 3 Measures of “Netting Project” in Shenzhen

Public Information Resource Base	Information Collector Team	Information Collection System	Social Management Network
Only set one unified information resource base and require government departments to access the information resource base.	Divide the whole city into 15000 grids and arrange 15000 information collectors to collect, manage, and share it.	Uniformly process and classify the information from information collectors and other sources, and eventually integrate with the data shared in the information resources platform to establish an underlying database.	The Social Management Network is a social service management platform based on the public information resource base. Social issues are channeled into the social management network, and various departments provide public services.

Source: Organized by authors

In the “Netting Project”, the government has built a professional team to carry out data collection and management as well as refined its public management to each community in Shenzhen. Furthermore, the unified information resource platform has greatly improved the efficiency of government services. However, there are no specific regulations for owners, managers and users in the process of sharing, leading to the problem of lack of clear authority and responsibility of data governance. In this period, the information silos still existed, and the share of government information is inefficient.

In 2015, Shenzhen Municipality formally issued the “Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Administration of Government Information Resources Sharing” (People’s Government of

Shenzhen Municipality, 2015). The new measures address the ownership, management, and use of government information, providing an institutional guarantee and institutional innovation for information sharing within the government.

Table 4 Information Resources Sharing of Government Data in Shenzhen

Ownership	Sharing	Co-construction	Application
The government has ownership of the government information collected by different departments within the government. The collection department has the management right while other departments have the use right.	Sharing of government information is a fundamental principle, and non-sharing is the exception. Information that cannot be shared must be justified and requires approval by the relevant department.	The basic database, thematic database, and shared platform are built and shared by various departments of the Shenzhen Municipal Government.	The purpose of sharing is to apply and improve governance through data mining and analysis.

Source: Organized by authors, referred to “Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Administration of Government Information Resources Sharing.”

Although the government has launched a series of policy documents to clarify the issue of data rights in the data governance process. Still, the smart city construction lacks top-level design and overall planning. Data is scattered across different levels of government and different departments, leading to multiple hotlines and many obstacles in aggregating data. Therefore, it is difficult to adopt emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big data to deliver high-level and high-quality services to the public.

3.3.4 New-type Smart City Construction

Traditional smart cities only focus on the use of new technologies to facilitate urbanization. Therefore, they lack superior design and lead to the problem of various information chimneys and silos in the city. The new-type smart city is a complex system of "holistic planning," "people-oriented," and "sharing," aiming to promote the integration of information, data and technology to achieve

cross-level, cross-regional, cross-sector, cross-business, cross-platform collaborative data management and services(SUN, 2019).

In 2015, Shenzhen became one of the pilot cities of the new-type smart city. Besides universities and research institutions, more and more market participants are also involved in the superior design and holistic planning of smart cities, such as the China Electronic Technology Group Corporation that used to engage in the construction of smart applications in the past. By breaking the information chimney and promoting information integration, the government's administrative efficiency under the new-type smart city has been dramatically improved. For example, Shenzhen is the first to implement "Process and Approve in seconds" in the government departments. (Shenzhen Press, 2018). According to the "The Overall Plan of Shenzhen Municipal Government for new-type smart city construction," Shenzhen will cooperate with local high-tech enterprises to establish a smart city and they plan to reach "Six One" goals by 2020, including "One Picture Full Perception," "One Platform for Integrated Operation and Linkage," "One Number in Shenzhen," "Enjoy Life with One Screen," "One Key to Know the Overall Situation" and "One-stop Innovation and Entrepreneurship" (Deloitte, 2019). These six goals of the new-type smart city correspond to cases of government-enterprise cooperation and enterprise from different industries began to participate in the smart city ecosystem. In this period, the roles of government and enterprise change in the field of city management in Shenzhen. On one hand, the government began to transform from a service provider to a service supervisor; on the other hand, enterprises use the industry's resources to develop smart city and transfer their roles to the public service operators, further exploring the supply side of the public service market.

Compared to the internal circulation of government information in traditional smart cities, the new-type smart cities pay more attention to the convergence and integration of data resources from various sources, emphasizing the interconnection and information sharing between government and social institutions to form a centralized government Big data resource management center in the city and to provide a unified data-sharing platform for departments to carry out smart applications. Shenzhen has successively launched the "Action Plan of Shenzhen Municipal Government for promoting Big Data Development (2016-2018)" "Implementation Plan for the Construction of Shenzhen City Big Data Center." These plans provide a superior design for the development of a new-type smart city in Shenzhen, including the improvement of 6 underlying databases (e.g., population and housing databases) and the construction of 20 thematic

databases (e.g., health security, education, and other livelihood fields). The Shenzhen, Big Data Resource Management Center, was also established to unify the data management of government departments at all levels, establish a unified Big data platform for government affairs, and achieve information sharing in Shenzhen (WU,2019).

Figure 3 The Model of Shenzhen New-type Smart City Source: Shenzhen New-type Smart City Design Concept and Practice, CETC, 2017

In the era of new-type smart cities, the scope of data openness has been extended from the government to the whole society and at the same time, the economic benefits brought by the data openness are growing. However, the value of data is rarely recognized in the production activities and for enterprise participated in the smart city, their data assets are challenging to secure. This may hinder the integration of government and social data and the creation of public value.

To solve this problem, in April 2020, China issued the "Opinions of the CPC Central Committee and the State Council on Improving the Systems and Mechanisms for Market-based Allocation of Factors of Production," where data was regarded for the first time as a new factor of production equal to land, labor, capital, and technology (Xinhua News Agency, 2020).

Table 6 Measures to Facilitate the Value of Data Factor in China

Key Points	Detailed Measures
<p>Facilitate the open and sharing of government data;</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Share the government data to facilitate the digital governance of government and the development of Big data industry. Therefore, the government should be responsible for the data sharing, using, management and security protection mechanisms; 2) Strengthen the top-level design and improve the shared performance appraisal mechanism to encourage all government levels to participate in the data sharing; 3) Establish the unified data-sharing platform and use emerging techniques to process and analyze the data; 4) Clarify the specific process of sharing open data and improve the whole life cycle management specifications such as data selection, review, collection, release, and offline collection. At the same time, relevant standard rules are formulated to clearly define the overall standards, terminology standards, metadata format standards, interface specifications, platform construction standards, etc. for data openness.
<p>Improve the resource value of public data;</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Explore the data application scenarios in society. Enhance the data flow through the business application and improve the value of data. 2) Coordinate government data resources and public data resources and establish a big data platform—open themes data to the society. 3) Accelerate data legislation and solve the problem of "unwilling to share." Formulating data standards and regulations. Enhance the supervision of Internet companies with massive data resources to avoid the leaking of sensitive data.
<p>Enhance the integration of data resources and security protection.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clarify data ownership. 2) Clarify the data pricing mechanism and measurement mechanism. 3) Enhance the market supervision mechanism. 4) Strengthen the data security protection mechanism.

Source: Organized by authors, referred to "Opinions of the CPC Central Committee and the State Council on Improving the Systems and Mechanisms for Market-based Allocation of Factors of Production."

3.4 Data Security and Privacy Protection

With the widespread application of emerging technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data and Cloud Computing, China's smart cities are facing the explosive development of data volumes. While benefiting from the data governance, data security has aroused the extensive concerns in the whole society. Data convergency and opening increase the risk of data leaks and privacy disclosure. To tackle these challenges, China is engaging in the laws and regulations formulations for data security and privacy protection in recent years.

3.4.1 "Measures for Data Security Management (Draft for Comments) "

In 2019, the Cyberspace Administration of China issued the "Measures for Data Security Management (Draft for Comments) " (After this referred to as the Measures), which is regarded as China's "General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)". Compared to the "Cybersecurity Law of the People's Republic of China" issued in 2016, the Measures focus more on the concept of data security, providing a legal protection for personal information and important data. Before the release of the Measures, China has introduced several policy documents on the protection of personal information, such as the "Information security technology—Personal information security specification", however these policies rarely have the legal force. Thus, the Measures can be regarded as the first legal regulations on data security in China.

The Measures are applicable to both private and public sectors and individuals, including "Network operators," "Government departments," and "Personal Information. " Besides, the Measures clarify the definition of terms "Network data," "Personal data," and "Important data." A clear definition promotes the standardized guideline for private and public sectors to protect personal privacy and data security.

“**Network operator**” means the owners and administrators of the network as well as network service providers.
 “**Personal information subject**” means the natural person identified or connected by the personal information.
 “**Network data**” means all kinds of electronic data collected, stored, transmitted, processed, and generated.
 “**Personal information**” means all kinds of information recorded in electronic or other forms, which can be used, independently or in combination with other information, to identify a natural person's identity, including but not limited to the natural person's name, date of birth, identity certificate number, biometric information, address, and telephone number.

“Important data” means the kind of data, if divulged, may directly affect national security, economic security, social stability, public health, and security, such as undisclosed government information, large-scale population, genetic health, geographic, mineral resources. Relevant data usually does not include information related to enterprises' production and operation, internal management information, or personal information.

Source: Drawn by authors and translated by Covington & Burling

The Measures have clarified provisions for the data activities such as the collection, storage, transmission, process and use of data, as well as the protection, supervision, and administration of cybersecurity. These provisions would help private sectors and individuals that participated in the data activity in the guidance of privacy protection and data security. To be specific, the Measures pay more attention on the protection of personal information. In Chapter 3, Articles 21,22 and 27 stress the users' consent right. Besides, the Measures have clear provision for corporate governance structures. In Chapter 2, Articles 17 and 18 require network operators to specify person responsible for data security.

Chapter 2 Data Collection

"Rules for collection and use" and "Record system"

Article 8 provides that network operators should develop and disclose the rules for the collection and use of data. Network operators shall register in the local cybersecurity for the record. The recorded "Rules for collection and use" shall include the purposes, types, volume, frequency, methods, the scope of the personal information to be collected and used; the place of storage, retention period and what the network operator will do with personal data after the retention period expires; the ways and methods for the data subject to withdraw consent and to access, correct and delete personal information; the rules to be followed when providing personal information to others.

"The person responsible for data security."

Articles 17 and 18 provide that the network operators shall specify the person responsible for data security when collecting essential data or personally sensitive information for business operations. The responsibilities and obligations of the person responsible for data security include formulate data protection plans, organize data security risk assessment, report to relevant government agencies and cybersecurity administrations the handling of data security protection and incidents, accept and handle the complaints, and reports of users.

Chapter 3 Process and Use of Data

"The protection for personal data and important data."

Articles 19, 20, and 23 provide that network operators shall take measures to protect personal data and valuable data and delete personal data when the data exceeds the

retention period or users reject the push information.

"Protection of users' consent right and timely response."

Article 21, 22, 26, and 27 highlights the protection of users' consent right and timely response when receiving reasonable requests, reports, and complaints from users.

"Data security risk assessment."

Article 27 to 30 stresses that when network operators provide personal information to any other person, or publish, share, sell and transfer data across borders, or connect to the third-party apps, the network operators shall assess potential security risks and report to the relevant department for approval. When occurring data security incidents, network operators shall assume all or part of the liability unless they can prove that they are not at fault.

Chapter 4 Supervision and Regulation of Data Security

"The regulatory authority of data security."

Article 33, 34, 36 clarify the responsibilities of different government departments in protecting data security. A cyberspace administration shall supervise the network operators to implement data security management obligations. The national cyberspace administration and the State Council's market regulatory department shall be responsible for the security authentications. The relevant competent departments of the State Council shall be responsible for the security protection of data provided by network operators.

"Supervision, management, and punishment for network operators."

Article 35 and 37 provide that network operators shall inform the users promptly when security incidents occur as well as the punishment measures such as confiscating the violator's illegal income from there, suspending relevant business operation when network operators violate the provision of the Measure or the laws.

Source: Organized by authors and referred to "Measures for Data Security Management."

However, there are places for improvement in the Measures. For example, the policy maker should consider the feasibility of regulations and policies. Though the Measures innovatively propose the "Record System" to review and manage the data security mechanism of the network operators, the number of subjects and the volume of data could be very large due to the dynamic real-time data and the wide range of network operators. Besides, compared to the large fines imposed on companies under the "GDPR", the Measures implement softer penalty measures such as admonition and public expose.

3.4.2 "Regulations of Shenzhen Special Economic Zone on Data (Consultation Draft)"

As mentioned before, China has introduced the concept of data factors and proposed new management measures to

data security. These measures reduce data users' concerns about privacy and data security while protecting data assets and playing the multiplier effect of data in improving productivity. With the arrival of the Big data era, the data owner has driven the intensive discussions in society. As a pioneer in the digital economy and smart city, Shenzhen has announced: "Regulations of Shenzhen Special Economic Zone on Data (Consultation Draft)" (After this referred to as the Regulations) in July 2020, which first mentioned data rights and the Shenzhen-Hong Kong-Macau data. The data right brings a new perspective in China that the digital economy should consider data security, data privacy while developing the digital industry.

Compared to the "Measures for Data Security Management (Draft for Comments)," the Regulations are more detailed in terms of data classification, data activities, and security guarantees. For example, the Regulations have detailed provisions on "public data." That indicates that as China moves from e-government and traditional smart cities to new smart cities, data resources have expanded from government information resources to diversified data such as Internet and enterprise data. Besides, internal-used government information platforms have changed into the city Big data platform that is more accessible to multiple parties.

Meanwhile, Shenzhen proposed the data integration mechanism and data cross-border international cooperation mechanisms in Shenzhen, Hong Kong, and Macao area in the Regulations, which covers the establishment of a free economic zone for cross-border data circulation, the data white list mechanism. As the start point of China's reform and opening up, Shenzhen will play an exemplary role in data exchange and international (regional) cooperation in the future.

"Public Data" and "Government data."
"Definition of public data" and "Definition of government data."
 "Public data" refers to the various types of data and their secondary data collected or generated and recorded or saved in a particular form when the public management and service agencies perform their duties or provide public management and services following the law.
 "Government data" refers to various data resources collected, generated, stored, and managed when government departments at all levels and their technical support centers perform their duties according to the law.
"Principals of the sharing of public data."
 "Public data" should be shared between public management and service agencies and with no sharing as the exception.

"Data Rights"
"Definition of data ownership."
 Following the law, data ownership empowers data right holders to

make independent decisions, control, process, receive gains, and receive compensation for specific data.
"Data Rights for the person and the public."
 "Natural persons" have data rights for their data following the law;
 "Public data" is a new type of state-owned asset. Its data rights belong to the state; "Data factor market participants" have the data rights of the legally collected data and the copyright of the data generated by themselves.

Source: Organized by authors and referred to "Regulations of Shenzhen Special Economic Zone on Data (Consultation Draft)"

Overall, the Regulations provide an innovative perspective of data rights as it clearly defines the public data and the data rights for the public data and individual data. However, there is a lack of instructions for public data categories and the definition related to personal information may be inconsistent in different policies and regulations, which may confuse enterprises and individuals in the implementation of data security management and privacy protection.

4 Conclusion

By interviewing the relevant high-tech enterprise co-constructing the Shenzhen smart cities and reviewing the government's public information and existing literature, some implications could be concluded. With a solid basis of information infrastructure and a complete government information resources sharing mechanism, Shenzhen's smart city is moving towards a sustainable development path characterized by "people-oriented," "innovation," "sharing," and "security."

Firstly, for small open data software, besides, to directly outsourcing smart city data projects to enterprises, the government can also adopt innovative modes such as organizing solicitation of software design works. This approach can not only raise the public's attention to smart cities but also promote public participation in smart city design.

Secondly, the Shenzhen Municipal Government is the leader in smart city construction. It has issued many documents and supporting policies to guide the collection, sharing, and application of data and many policy concepts such as "sharing principle" are ahead of other cities. At the same time, the government encourages enterprises to participate in the construction of smart cities through cooperation, such as "general contracting, subcontracting, and government purchase."

Third, considering the regulations on privacy protection and data security is framing in recent years. However, policymakers have started to issue relevant provisions to safeguard the privacy rights of smart city participants, and the relevant concepts are still not clear enough. Several relevant documents refer to the protection of personal-related information, but personal data is inconsistent. For example, the scope of personal information in the Measures does not mention personal credit information. Therefore, policymakers still need a unified framework of rules to improve the mechanism standards covering technology, management, supervision, and security while formulating the regulations and laws.

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